

```

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scenario5P1S1D2B2
scenario6P1S1D2B3scenario7P1S1D3B1scenario8P1S1D3B2scenario9P1S1D3B3
scenario10P1S2D1B1
scenario11P1S2D1B2scenario12P1S2D1B3Tscenario13P1S2D2B1scenario14P1S
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scenario16P1S2D3B1scenario17P1S2D3B2scenario18P1S2D3B3scenario19P2S1
D1B1 scenario20P2S1D1B2
scenario21P2S1D1B3scenario22P2S1D2B1scenario23P2S1D2B2scenario24P2S1
D2B3 scenario25P2S1D3B1
scenario26P2S1D3B2scenario27P2S1D3B3scenario28P2S2D1B1scenario29P2S2
D1B2 scenario30P2S2D1B3
scenario31P2S2D2B1scenario32P2S2D2B2scenario33P2S2D2B3scenario34P2S2
D3B1 scenario35P2S2D3B2
scenario36P2S2D3B3
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Behavior 3 Polynomial
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Physical.activity*Diagnosis Smoking.habits*Diagnosis Physical.activity*
Smoking.habits*Diagnosis
Physical.activity*Behavior Smoking.habits*Behavior Physical.activity*Sm
oking.habits*Behavior

```

Diagnosis*Behavior Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior Smoking.habits*
 Diagnosis*Behavior
 Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior.

General Linear Model

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Dependent Variable		
1	1	1	1	scenario1P1S 1D1B1		
			2	scenario2P1S 1D1B2		
			3	scenario3P1S 1D1B3		
		2	1	2	1	scenario4P1S 1D2B1
					2	scenario5P1S 1D2B2
					3	scenario6P1S 1D2B3
		3	1	3	1	scenario7P1S 1D3B1
					2	scenario8P1S 1D3B2
					3	scenario9P1S 1D3B3
2	2	1	1	scenario10P1 S2D1B1		
			2	scenario11P1 S2D1B2		
			3	scenario12P1 S2D1B3T		
		2	2	2	1	scenario13P1 S2D2B1
					2	scenario14P1 S2D2B2
					3	scenario15P1 S2D2B3
		3	2	3	1	scenario16P1 S2D3B1
					2	scenario17P1 S2D3B2
					3	scenario18P1 S2D3B3

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Dependent Variable	
2	1	1	1	scenario19P2 S1D1B1	
			2	scenario20P2 S1D1B2	
			3	scenario21P2 S1D1B3	
		2	1	1	scenario22P2 S1D2B1
				2	scenario23P2 S1D2B2
				3	scenario24P2 S1D2B3
		3	1	1	scenario25P2 S1D3B1
				2	scenario26P2 S1D3B2
				3	scenario27P2 S1D3B3
2	2	1	1	scenario28P2 S2D1B1	
			2	scenario29P2 S2D1B2	
			3	scenario30P2 S2D1B3	
		2	1	1	scenario31P2 S2D2B1
				2	scenario32P2 S2D2B2
				3	scenario33P2 S2D2B3
		3	1	1	scenario34P2 S2D3B1
				2	scenario35P2 S2D3B2
				3	scenario36P2 S2D3B3

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,275	47,430 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,725	47,430 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,379	47,430 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,379	47,430 ^b	1,000	125,000
Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,395	81,628 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,605	81,628 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,653	81,628 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,653	81,628 ^b	1,000	125,000
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,283	24,442 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,717	24,442 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,394	24,442 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,394	24,442 ^b	2,000	124,000
Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,778	217,870 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,222	217,870 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	3,514	217,870 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	3,514	217,870 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,001	,155 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,999	,155 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,001	,155 ^b	1,000	125,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,001	,155 ^b	1,000	125,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,077	5,194 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,923	5,194 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,084	5,194 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,084	5,194 ^b	2,000	124,000
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,053	3,454 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,947	3,454 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,056	3,454 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,056	3,454 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,003	,188 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,997	,188 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,003	,188 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,003	,188 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,141	10,177 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,859	10,177 ^b	2,000	124,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,000	,275
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,275
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,275
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,275
Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,000	,395
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,395
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,395
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,395
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,000	,283
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,283
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,283
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,283
Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,778
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,778
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,778
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,778
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,694	,001
	Wilks' Lambda	,694	,001
	Hotelling's Trace	,694	,001
	Roy's Largest Root	,694	,001
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,007	,077
	Wilks' Lambda	,007	,077
	Hotelling's Trace	,007	,077
	Roy's Largest Root	,007	,077
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,035	,053
	Wilks' Lambda	,035	,053
	Hotelling's Trace	,035	,053
	Roy's Largest Root	,035	,053
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,829	,003
	Wilks' Lambda	,829	,003
	Hotelling's Trace	,829	,003
	Roy's Largest Root	,829	,003
Physical.activity * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,141
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,141

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
	Hotelling's Trace	,164	10,177 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,164	10,177 ^b	2,000	124,000
Smoking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,356	34,295 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,644	34,295 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,553	34,295 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,553	34,295 ^b	2,000	124,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,003	,189 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,997	,189 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,003	,189 ^b	2,000	124,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,003	,189 ^b	2,000	124,000
Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,385	19,057 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,615	19,057 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,625	19,057 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,625	19,057 ^b	4,000	122,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,042	1,349 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,958	1,349 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,044	1,349 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,044	1,349 ^b	4,000	122,000
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,040	1,280 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,960	1,280 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,042	1,280 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,042	1,280 ^b	4,000	122,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,061	1,978 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,939	1,978 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,065	1,978 ^b	4,000	122,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,065	1,978 ^b	4,000	122,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,141
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,141
Smoking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,356
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,356
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,356
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,356
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,828	,003
	Wilks' Lambda	,828	,003
	Hotelling's Trace	,828	,003
	Roy's Largest Root	,828	,003
Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,000	,385
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,385
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,385
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,385
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,256	,042
	Wilks' Lambda	,256	,042
	Hotelling's Trace	,256	,042
	Roy's Largest Root	,256	,042
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,282	,040
	Wilks' Lambda	,282	,040
	Hotelling's Trace	,282	,040
	Roy's Largest Root	,282	,040
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Pillai's Trace	,102	,061
	Wilks' Lambda	,102	,061
	Hotelling's Trace	,102	,061
	Roy's Largest Root	,102	,061

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Smoking.habits + Diagnosis + Behavior + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behavior + Smoking.habits * Behavior + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior + Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

b. Exact statistic

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Epsilon ^b Greenhouse-Geisser
Physical.activity	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Smoking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Diagnosis	,302	148,618	2	,000	,589
Behavior	,902	12,814	2	,002	,911
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,998	,276	2	,871	,998
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,961	4,996	2	,082	,962
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,985	1,847	2	,397	,985
Physical.activity * Behavior	,977	2,940	2	,230	,977
Smoking.habits * Behavior	,994	,792	2	,673	,994
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	,986	1,739	2	,419	,986
Diagnosis * Behavior	,098	287,277	9	,000	,457
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	,899	13,208	9	,153	,954
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,704	43,280	9	,000	,875
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,829	23,152	9	,006	,916

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Epsilon ^b	
	Huynh-Feldt	Lower-bound
Physical.activity	1,000	1,000
Smoking.habits	1,000	1,000
Diagnosis	,591	,500
Behavior	,923	,500
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	1,000	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	1,000	,500
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,977	,500
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	1,000	,500
Physical.activity * Behavior	,992	,500
Smoking.habits * Behavior	1,000	,500
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	1,000	,500
Diagnosis * Behavior	,464	,250
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	,987	,250
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,903	,250
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	,947	,250

Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Smoking.habits + Diagnosis + Behavior + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behavior + Smoking.habits * Behavior + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior + Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

b. May be used to adjust the degrees of freedom for the averaged tests of significance. Corrected tests are displayed in the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table.

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	227,122	1	227,122
	Greenhouse-Geisser	227,122	1,000	227,122
	Huynh-Feldt	227,122	1,000	227,122
	Lower-bound	227,122	1,000	227,122
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed	598,573	125	4,789
	Greenhouse-Geisser	598,573	125,000	4,789
	Huynh-Feldt	598,573	125,000	4,789
	Lower-bound	598,573	125,000	4,789
Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	403,573	1	403,573
	Greenhouse-Geisser	403,573	1,000	403,573
	Huynh-Feldt	403,573	1,000	403,573
	Lower-bound	403,573	1,000	403,573
Error(Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	618,010	125	4,944
	Greenhouse-Geisser	618,010	125,000	4,944
	Huynh-Feldt	618,010	125,000	4,944
	Lower-bound	618,010	125,000	4,944
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	831,596	2	415,798
	Greenhouse-Geisser	831,596	1,178	706,176
	Huynh-Feldt	831,596	1,182	703,453
	Lower-bound	831,596	1,000	831,596
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	2523,627	250	10,095
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2523,627	147,201	17,144
	Huynh-Feldt	2523,627	147,770	17,078
	Lower-bound	2523,627	125,000	20,189
Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	16588,743	2	8294,371
	Greenhouse-Geisser	16588,743	1,821	9108,684
	Huynh-Feldt	16588,743	1,847	8983,029
	Lower-bound	16588,743	1,000	16588,743
Error(Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	7201,313	250	28,805
	Greenhouse-Geisser	7201,313	227,650	31,633
	Huynh-Feldt	7201,313	230,834	31,197
	Lower-bound	7201,313	125,000	57,611
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	,212	1	,212
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,212	1,000	,212
	Huynh-Feldt	,212	1,000	,212
	Lower-bound	,212	1,000	,212

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	47,430	,000	,275
	Greenhouse-Geisser	47,430	,000	,275
	Huynh-Feldt	47,430	,000	,275
	Lower-bound	47,430	,000	,275
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	81,628	,000	,395
	Greenhouse-Geisser	81,628	,000	,395
	Huynh-Feldt	81,628	,000	,395
	Lower-bound	81,628	,000	,395
Error(Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	41,191	,000	,248
	Greenhouse-Geisser	41,191	,000	,248
	Huynh-Feldt	41,191	,000	,248
	Lower-bound	41,191	,000	,248
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	287,946	,000	,697
	Greenhouse-Geisser	287,946	,000	,697
	Huynh-Feldt	287,946	,000	,697
	Lower-bound	287,946	,000	,697
Error(Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	,155	,694	,001
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,155	,694	,001
	Huynh-Feldt	,155	,694	,001
	Lower-bound	,155	,694	,001

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	170,371	125	1,363
	Greenhouse-Geisser	170,371	125,000	1,363
	Huynh-Feldt	170,371	125,000	1,363
	Lower-bound	170,371	125,000	1,363
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	15,138	2	7,569
	Greenhouse-Geisser	15,138	1,996	7,586
	Huynh-Feldt	15,138	2,000	7,569
	Lower-bound	15,138	1,000	15,138
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	345,418	250	1,382
	Greenhouse-Geisser	345,418	249,446	1,385
	Huynh-Feldt	345,418	250,000	1,382
	Lower-bound	345,418	125,000	2,763
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	13,821	2	6,911
	Greenhouse-Geisser	13,821	1,924	7,184
	Huynh-Feldt	13,821	1,953	7,075
	Lower-bound	13,821	1,000	13,821
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	414,179	250	1,657
	Greenhouse-Geisser	414,179	240,502	1,722
	Huynh-Feldt	414,179	244,185	1,696
	Lower-bound	414,179	125,000	3,313
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	,561	2	,281
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,561	1,971	,285
	Huynh-Feldt	,561	2,000	,281
	Lower-bound	,561	1,000	,561
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	337,439	250	1,350
	Greenhouse-Geisser	337,439	246,357	1,370
	Huynh-Feldt	337,439	250,000	1,350
	Lower-bound	337,439	125,000	2,700
Physical.activity * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	31,399	2	15,699
	Greenhouse-Geisser	31,399	1,954	16,067
	Huynh-Feldt	31,399	1,985	15,819
	Lower-bound	31,399	1,000	31,399
Error(Physical. activity*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	368,990	250	1,476
	Greenhouse-Geisser	368,990	244,276	1,511
	Huynh-Feldt	368,990	248,109	1,487
	Lower-bound	368,990	125,000	2,952

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	5,478	,005	,042
	Greenhouse-Geisser	5,478	,005	,042
	Huynh-Feldt	5,478	,005	,042
	Lower-bound	5,478	,021	,042
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	4,171	,017	,032
	Greenhouse-Geisser	4,171	,018	,032
	Huynh-Feldt	4,171	,017	,032
	Lower-bound	4,171	,043	,032
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	,208	,812	,002
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,208	,809	,002
	Huynh-Feldt	,208	,812	,002
	Lower-bound	,208	,649	,002
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	10,637	,000	,078
	Greenhouse-Geisser	10,637	,000	,078
	Huynh-Feldt	10,637	,000	,078
	Lower-bound	10,637	,001	,078
Error(Physical. activity*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Smoking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	182,587	2	91,294
	Greenhouse-Geisser	182,587	1,987	91,875
	Huynh-Feldt	182,587	2,000	91,294
	Lower-bound	182,587	1,000	182,587
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	616,246	250	2,465
	Greenhouse-Geisser	616,246	248,419	2,481
	Huynh-Feldt	616,246	250,000	2,465
	Lower-bound	616,246	125,000	4,930
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	,536	2	,268
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,536	1,973	,272
	Huynh-Feldt	,536	2,000	,268
	Lower-bound	,536	1,000	,536
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	373,964	250	1,496
	Greenhouse-Geisser	373,964	246,567	1,517
	Huynh-Feldt	373,964	250,000	1,496
	Lower-bound	373,964	125,000	2,992
Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1339,321	4	334,830
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1339,321	1,829	732,171
	Huynh-Feldt	1339,321	1,855	721,996
	Lower-bound	1339,321	1,000	1339,321
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	3025,290	500	6,051
	Greenhouse-Geisser	3025,290	228,656	13,231
	Huynh-Feldt	3025,290	231,878	13,047
	Lower-bound	3025,290	125,000	24,202
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	5,514	4	1,379
	Greenhouse-Geisser	5,514	3,814	1,446
	Huynh-Feldt	5,514	3,949	1,396
	Lower-bound	5,514	1,000	5,514
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	521,097	500	1,042
	Greenhouse-Geisser	521,097	476,764	1,093
	Huynh-Feldt	521,097	493,641	1,056
	Lower-bound	521,097	125,000	4,169
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	7,675	4	1,919
	Greenhouse-Geisser	7,675	3,498	2,194
	Huynh-Feldt	7,675	3,611	2,125
	Lower-bound	7,675	1,000	7,675

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Smoking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	37,036	,000	,229
	Greenhouse-Geisser	37,036	,000	,229
	Huynh-Feldt	37,036	,000	,229
	Lower-bound	37,036	,000	,229
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	,179	,836	,001
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,179	,833	,001
	Huynh-Feldt	,179	,836	,001
	Lower-bound	,179	,673	,001
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	55,339	,000	,307
	Greenhouse-Geisser	55,339	,000	,307
	Huynh-Feldt	55,339	,000	,307
	Lower-bound	55,339	,000	,307
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1,323	,260	,010
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,323	,262	,010
	Huynh-Feldt	1,323	,261	,010
	Lower-bound	1,323	,252	,010
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	1,482	,206	,012
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,482	,213	,012
	Huynh-Feldt	1,482	,211	,012
	Lower-bound	1,482	,226	,012

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	647,159	500	1,294
	Greenhouse-Geisser	647,159	437,301	1,480
	Huynh-Feldt	647,159	451,434	1,434
	Lower-bound	647,159	125,000	5,177
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	15,522	4	3,881
	Greenhouse-Geisser	15,522	3,665	4,235
	Huynh-Feldt	15,522	3,789	4,096
	Lower-bound	15,522	1,000	15,522
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed	686,645	500	1,373
	Greenhouse-Geisser	686,645	458,128	1,499
	Huynh-Feldt	686,645	473,682	1,450
	Lower-bound	686,645	125,000	5,493

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Sphericity Assumed	2,826	,024	,022
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,826	,028	,022
	Huynh-Feldt	2,826	,027	,022
	Lower-bound	2,826	,095	,022
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior
Physical.activity	Linear			
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear			
Smoking.habits		Linear		
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear		
Diagnosis			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Behavior				Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Behavior)				Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear		
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear		
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity	Linear				227,122
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				598,573
Smoking.habits		Linear			403,573
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			618,010
Diagnosis			Linear		560,583
			Quadratic		271,012
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		1815,083
			Quadratic		708,543
Behavior				Linear	16585,557
				Quadratic	3,186
Error(Behavior)				Linear	4721,443
				Quadratic	2479,870
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,212
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			170,371
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		14,862
			Quadratic		,276
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		180,804
			Quadratic		164,613
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		8,679
			Quadratic		5,143
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		214,821
			Quadratic		199,357
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,190
			Quadratic		,371
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		152,976
			Quadratic		184,463
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	31,370
				Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	193,630
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	180,107
				Quadratic	
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	332,226
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	df
Physical.activity	Linear				1
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				125
Smoking.habits		Linear			1
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			125
Diagnosis			Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Behavior				Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Behavior)				Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			125
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		125
			Quadratic		125
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	125
				Quadratic	125

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Linear				227,122
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				4,789
Smoking.habits		Linear			403,573
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			4,944
Diagnosis			Linear		560,583
			Quadratic		271,012
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		14,521
			Quadratic		5,668
Behavior				Linear	16585,557
				Quadratic	3,186
Error(Behavior)				Linear	37,772
				Quadratic	19,839
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,212
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			1,363
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		14,862
			Quadratic		,276
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		1,446
			Quadratic		1,317
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		8,679
			Quadratic		5,143
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		1,719
			Quadratic		1,595
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,190
			Quadratic		,371
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,224
			Quadratic		1,476
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	31,370
				Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	1,549
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	180,107
				Quadratic	
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	2,658
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	F
Physical.activity	Linear				47,430
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Smoking.habits		Linear			81,628
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		38,606
			Quadratic		47,812
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	439,102
				Quadratic	,161
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,155
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		10,275
			Quadratic		,209
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		5,050
			Quadratic		3,225
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,156
			Quadratic		,251
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	20,252
				Quadratic	,020
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	67,765
				Quadratic	1,092
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Sig.
Physical.activity	Linear				,000
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Smoking.habits		Linear			,000
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,000
			Quadratic		,000
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,689
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,694
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,002
			Quadratic		,648
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,026
			Quadratic		,075
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,694
			Quadratic		,617
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,887
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,298
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Linear				,275
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Smoking.habits		Linear			,395
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,236
			Quadratic		,277
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behavior				Linear	,778
				Quadratic	,001
Error(Behavior)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,001
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,076
			Quadratic		,002
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,039
			Quadratic		,025
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,001
			Quadratic		,002
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behavior	Linear			Linear	,139
				Quadratic	,000
Error(Physical.activity*Behavior)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behavior		Linear		Linear	,352
				Quadratic	,009
Error(Smoking.habits*Behavior)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,190
				Quadratic	,346
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	170,143
				Quadratic	203,821
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	931,002
				Quadratic	96,006
			Quadratic	Linear	300,447
				Quadratic	11,866
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	1592,248
				Quadratic	523,827
			Quadratic	Linear	614,553
				Quadratic	294,662
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,794
				Quadratic	1,788
			Quadratic	Linear	2,794
				Quadratic	,138
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	119,706
				Quadratic	142,795
			Quadratic	Linear	122,956
				Quadratic	135,640
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	5,365
				Quadratic	,095
			Quadratic	Linear	1,339
				Quadratic	,875
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	157,885
				Quadratic	195,405
			Quadratic	Linear	160,827
				Quadratic	133,042
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1,050
				Quadratic	1,006
			Quadratic	Linear	10,500
				Quadratic	2,966
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	141,450
				Quadratic	155,577
			Quadratic	Linear	208,417
				Quadratic	181,200

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	df
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125
			Quadratic	Linear	125
				Quadratic	125

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean Square
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,190
				Quadratic	,346
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	1,361
				Quadratic	1,631
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	931,002
				Quadratic	96,006
			Quadratic	Linear	300,447
				Quadratic	11,866
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	12,738
				Quadratic	4,191
			Quadratic	Linear	4,916
				Quadratic	2,357
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,794
				Quadratic	1,788
			Quadratic	Linear	2,794
				Quadratic	,138
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	,958
				Quadratic	1,142
			Quadratic	Linear	,984
				Quadratic	1,085
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	5,365
				Quadratic	,095
			Quadratic	Linear	1,339
				Quadratic	,875
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	1,263
				Quadratic	1,563
			Quadratic	Linear	1,287
				Quadratic	1,064
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1,050
				Quadratic	1,006
			Quadratic	Linear	10,500
				Quadratic	2,966
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1,132
				Quadratic	1,245
			Quadratic	Linear	1,667
				Quadratic	1,450

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	F
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,140
				Quadratic	,212
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	73,089
				Quadratic	22,910
			Quadratic	Linear	61,111
				Quadratic	5,034
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,829
				Quadratic	1,565
			Quadratic	Linear	2,841
				Quadratic	,127
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	4,248
				Quadratic	,061
			Quadratic	Linear	1,041
				Quadratic	,822
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,928
				Quadratic	,808
			Quadratic	Linear	6,297
				Quadratic	2,046
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Sig.
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,709
				Quadratic	,646
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,000
			Quadratic	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,027
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,364
				Quadratic	,213
			Quadratic	Linear	,094
				Quadratic	,722
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	,041
				Quadratic	,805
			Quadratic	Linear	,310
				Quadratic	,366
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,337
				Quadratic	,370
			Quadratic	Linear	,013
				Quadratic	,155
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior	Linear	Linear		Linear	,001
				Quadratic	,002
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behavior)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behavior			Linear	Linear	,369
				Quadratic	,155
			Quadratic	Linear	,328
				Quadratic	,039
Error(Diagnosis*Behavior)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear		Linear	Linear	,007
				Quadratic	,012
			Quadratic	Linear	,022
				Quadratic	,001
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior		Linear	Linear	Linear	,033
				Quadratic	,000
			Quadratic	Linear	,008
				Quadratic	,007
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,007
				Quadratic	,006
			Quadratic	Linear	,048
				Quadratic	,016
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behavior)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	205041,228	1	205041,228	2215,199	,000	,947
Error	11570,133	125	92,561			

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Physical.activity

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,947	,134	6,683	7,212
2	6,500	,158	6,186	6,813

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	,448 [*]	,065	,000	,319
2	1	-,448 [*]	,065	,000	-,576

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	,576
2	1	-,319

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,275	47,430 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,275
Wilks' lambda	,725	47,430 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,275
Hotelling's trace	,379	47,430 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,275
Roy's largest root	,379	47,430 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,275

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Physical.activity. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

2. Smoking.habits

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,425	,156	6,115	6,735
2	7,022	,136	6,752	7,291

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Smoking.habits	(J) Smoking.habits	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	-,597 [*]	,066	,000	-,727
2	1	,597 [*]	,066	,000	,466

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Smoking.habits	(J) Smoking.habits	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	-,466
2	1	,727

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,395	81,628 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,395
Wilks' lambda	,605	81,628 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,395
Hotelling's trace	,653	81,628 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,395
Roy's largest root	,653	81,628 ^a	1,000	125,000	,000	,395

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Smoking.habits. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

3. Diagnosis

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,466	,151	6,168	6,764
2	6,378	,154	6,073	6,682
3	7,327	,168	6,994	7,659

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence b...
					Lower Bound
1	2	,088	,047	,189	-,026
	3	-,861 [*]	,139	,000	-1,197
2	1	-,088	,047	,189	-,202
	3	-,949 [*]	,137	,000	-1,280
3	1	,861 [*]	,139	,000	,525
	2	,949 [*]	,137	,000	,618

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	95% Confidence Interval for ^b ..
		Upper Bound
1	2	,202
	3	-,525
2	1	,026
	3	-,618
3	1	1,197
	2	1,280

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,283	24,442 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,283
Wilks' lambda	,717	24,442 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,283
Hotelling's trace	,394	24,442 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,283
Roy's largest root	,394	24,442 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,283

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Diagnosis. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

4. Behavior

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	9,084	,091	8,904	9,264
2	6,686	,198	6,294	7,077
3	4,400	,228	3,949	4,851

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Behavior	(J) Behavior	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	2,398 [*]	,183	,000	1,955	2,841
	3	4,684 [*]	,224	,000	4,141	5,226
2	1	-2,398 [*]	,183	,000	-2,841	-1,955
	3	2,286 [*]	,176	,000	1,859	2,713
3	1	-4,684 [*]	,224	,000	-5,226	-4,141
	2	-2,286 [*]	,176	,000	-2,713	-1,859

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,778	217,870 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,778
Wilks' lambda	,222	217,870 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,778
Hotelling's trace	3,514	217,870 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,778
Roy's largest root	3,514	217,870 ^a	2,000	124,000	,000	,778

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Behavior. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

5. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,642	,146	6,354	6,930
	2	7,252	,131	6,993	7,511
2	1	6,208	,173	5,866	6,550
	2	6,791	,152	6,490	7,092

6. Physical.activity * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,754	,142	6,473	7,035
	2	6,612	,146	6,323	6,901
	3	7,475	,161	7,156	7,794
2	1	6,177	,170	5,841	6,513
	2	6,143	,172	5,802	6,483
	3	7,179	,182	6,818	7,539

7. Physical.activity * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	9,411	,076	9,261	9,562
	2	6,906	,192	6,526	7,286
	3	4,524	,227	4,074	4,973
2	1	8,757	,124	8,511	9,002
	2	6,466	,211	6,047	6,884
	3	4,276	,234	3,814	4,739

8. Smoking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,138	,163	5,815	6,460
	2	6,032	,171	5,694	6,370
	3	7,106	,185	6,740	7,471
2	1	6,794	,148	6,501	7,087
	2	6,724	,148	6,432	7,015
	3	7,548	,163	7,225	7,870

9. Smoking.habits * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	9,046	,103	8,842	9,250
	2	6,354	,225	5,910	6,799
	3	3,874	,243	3,394	4,354
2	1	9,122	,085	8,953	9,290
	2	7,017	,182	6,658	7,377
	3	4,926	,227	4,477	5,375

10. Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	9,183	,088	9,008	9,357
	2	6,629	,221	6,191	7,066
	3	3,585	,248	3,094	4,076
2	1	9,133	,103	8,930	9,336
	2	6,442	,225	5,996	6,889
	3	3,558	,245	3,073	4,042
3	1	8,937	,133	8,673	9,200
	2	6,986	,212	6,566	7,406
	3	6,058	,290	5,485	6,631

11. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
1	1	1	6,421	,156	6,111
		2	6,272	,164	5,947
		3	7,233	,176	6,884
	2	1	7,087	,144	6,802
		2	6,952	,145	6,666
		3	7,717	,163	7,394
2	1	1	5,854	,182	5,494
		2	5,791	,188	5,419
		3	6,979	,205	6,574
	2	1	6,500	,170	6,163
		2	6,495	,171	6,157
		3	7,378	,178	7,027

11. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	95% Confidence .
			Upper Bound
1	1	1	6,730
		2	6,598
		3	7,582
	2	1	7,373
		2	7,239
		3	8,039
2	1	1	6,215
		2	6,163
		3	7,384
	2	1	6,837
		2	6,833
		3	7,730

12. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval		
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
1	1	1	9,381	,089	9,204	9,558	
		2	6,556	,220	6,120	6,991	
		3	3,989	,243	3,509	4,470	
	2	1	9,442	,077	9,290	9,593	
		2	7,257	,183	6,894	7,619	
		3	5,058	,229	4,604	5,512	
	2	1	1	8,712	,138	8,438	8,986
			2	6,153	,240	5,678	6,629
			3	3,759	,249	3,266	4,252
2		1	8,802	,121	8,562	9,041	
		2	6,778	,196	6,390	7,165	
		3	4,794	,236	4,326	5,262	

13. Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	9,587	,065	9,460	9,715
		2	6,885	,221	6,448	7,322
		3	3,790	,252	3,291	4,288
	2	1	9,520	,087	9,348	9,691
		2	6,663	,219	6,230	7,096
		3	3,655	,252	3,156	4,154
	3	1	9,127	,136	8,857	9,397
		2	7,171	,212	6,752	7,590
		3	6,127	,291	5,551	6,703
2	1	1	8,778	,136	8,508	9,047
		2	6,373	,241	5,897	6,849
		3	3,381	,254	2,879	3,883
	2	1	8,746	,143	8,463	9,029
		2	6,222	,246	5,736	6,709
		3	3,460	,252	2,962	3,958
	3	1	8,746	,150	8,449	9,044
		2	6,802	,223	6,360	7,244
		3	5,988	,299	5,396	6,580

14. Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	9,163	,102	8,960	9,366
		2	6,246	,253	5,745	6,747
		3	3,004	,259	2,492	3,516
	2	1	9,063	,120	8,825	9,302
		2	6,091	,257	5,583	6,600
		3	2,940	,259	2,427	3,454
	3	1	8,913	,142	8,632	9,194
		2	6,726	,242	6,246	7,206
		3	5,679	,314	5,057	6,300
2	1	1	9,202	,088	9,028	9,377
		2	7,012	,208	6,601	7,423
		3	4,167	,257	3,658	4,676
	2	1	9,202	,094	9,017	9,388
		2	6,794	,211	6,376	7,211
		3	4,175	,256	3,667	4,682
	3	1	8,960	,137	8,688	9,232
		2	7,246	,208	6,834	7,658
		3	6,437	,283	5,877	6,996

15. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	Mean	Std. Error	95% ... Lower Bound	
1	1	1	1	9,595	,076	9,445	
			2	6,484	,262	5,966	
			3	3,183	,261	2,666	
		2	1	9,413	,130	9,155	
			2	6,254	,260	5,740	
			3	3,151	,268	2,621	
		3	1	9,135	,142	8,853	
			2	6,929	,240	6,453	
			3	5,635	,323	4,996	
	2	1	1	1	9,579	,071	9,439
				2	7,286	,215	6,860
				3	4,397	,277	3,849
			2	1	9,627	,066	9,496
				2	7,071	,219	6,637
				3	4,159	,271	3,623
3		1	9,119	,154	8,814		
		2	7,413	,217	6,983		
		3	6,619	,289	6,048		
2	1	1	1	8,730	,154	8,426	
			2	6,008	,280	5,455	
			3	2,825	,267	2,297	
		2	1	8,714	,167	8,383	
			2	5,929	,272	5,390	
			3	2,730	,265	2,206	
		3	1	8,690	,165	8,364	
			2	6,524	,263	6,002	
			3	5,722	,331	5,068	
	2	1	1	8,825	,147	8,535	
			2	6,738	,232	6,279	
			3	3,937	,261	3,419	
		2	1	8,778	,154	8,472	
			2	6,516	,240	6,040	
			3	4,190	,281	3,635	
3	1	8,802	,152	8,500			
	2	7,079	,223	6,637			
	3	6,254	,299	5,663			

15. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behavior

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behavior	95% Confidence .
				Upper Bound
1	1	1	1	9,745
			2	7,002
			3	3,700
		2	1	9,670
			2	6,768
			3	3,680
		3	1	9,416
			2	7,404
			3	6,274
	2	1	1	9,719
			2	7,712
			3	4,945
		2	1	9,758
			2	7,506
			3	4,694
		3	1	9,424
			2	7,842
			3	7,190
2	1	1	1	9,035
			2	6,561
			3	3,354
		2	1	9,046
			2	6,467
			3	3,254
		3	1	9,017
			2	7,045
			3	6,376
	2	1	1	9,115
			2	7,197
			3	4,454
		2	1	9,083
			2	6,991
			3	4,746
		3	1	9,103
			2	7,521
			3	6,845